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The Mosasaur

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COVER ART – The cover art was painted by Jason Poole and depicts a school of Mosasaurs.

INQUIRY-BASED FIELD TRIPS IN PALEONTOLOGY FOR STEM CLASSES

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ABSTRACT - Inquiry-based education is a way of teaching science that focuses on the methodology of science by engaging students in active observation, gathering and interpretation of evidence, and generating scientific hypotheses. The student is encouraged to construct an understanding of the natural world based on their own observations and rational thinking. I present eight field exercises for local instructors teaching paleontology and geology on the college and high school level based on inquiry practices.

INTRODUCTION

Inquiry-based educational strategies have become important pedagogical tools on every level, especially in science education. A quick peek at the recently revised New Jersey Standards for Science Education (state.nj.us/education/cccs.5.pdf) reveals that understanding the methodology and process of science is an important goal of the latest criteria for science education, and inquiry techniques are recommended as one good way to achieve this goal.

Inquiry-based education goes by a number of names, including active education, the inverted classroom, discovery, and experiential education. Geologists and paleontologists have always used this form of instruction, especially in labs and field trips. The objective in this approach is to encourage the student to observe for themselves, gather data, formulate hypotheses, and provide evidence to support their hypotheses. In other words, the idea here in STEM learning is to teach students how to approach a problem or situation through the classic scientific method.

Inquiry practice has its roots in the research and ideas of Jean Piaget (1896-1980), Swiss naturalist and child psychologist. Originally, he was interested in the

natural history of his native country, Switzerland, but as a teacher and parent Piaget became more

interested in child psychology and particularly cognitive development, the way in which juvenile humans grow into understanding the world around them. He posited several developmental stages during which the growing human from toddler to adult constructs an understanding of the world through direct observation and experience and later, use of logic. Particular stages of development will require different educational strategies keyed to the biological abilities and level of cognitive development the students have reached.

Inquiry-based education lends itself to encouraging students to observe their world and draw their own conclusions. Pure or “open” inquiry would impose no or few initial concepts or paradigms upon the student, and the teacher’s job is to let students draw all their own conclusions. But as one of my colleagues observed, “You cannot expect students in an introductory physics class to reconstruct the 400-year development of modern physics in a

semester or two “. So, the more common approach is guided inquiry, in which initial ideas and methodologies are introduced, a

specific question or problem is posed, and students are allowed to work out the solution largely through their own observations. This approach eschews classic “cookbook” experiments or exercises in which the student must adhere to a prescribed detailed procedure and the outcome is predetermined, and success is judged by adherence to procedure and how precisely accurate the results are. Inquiry emphasizes the “how” of science rather than rote memorization of facts or exactly following a prescribed recipe.

Inquiry approaches emphasize interdisciplinary connections to other subjects, attempting to place science in a context of historical developments and current concerns. So, some of these exercises are linked to local history and others to present day issues in the environment.

This paper presents some of the field exercises in paleontology I have developed over the course of several decades teaching for a number of Delaware Valley area colleges. As a formal exercise in inquiry based science education, these exercises were honed and refined largely as a result of participation in the Discovery Program of Rider University (Gallagher, 2012; Gallagher and Brown, 2013), although they represent the results of years of teaching in the field and lab. I have provided these exercises as examples of how an inquiry approach can be applied using local paleontological and geological sites, but these same kinds of field experiences could be replicated elsewhere using the same principles. The course level varied from general Science 100 introductory classes for freshman non-majors to more advanced undergraduate and graduate courses for majors. I have noted the course(s) in which particular exercises were used; course level determines the degree of sophistication needed, and each exercise can be adjusted accordingly. Some of the exercises could, for example, easily be adapted for a high school or middle school earth science course.

Field Trip #1- Rocks and Geologic Time, Valley Forge National Historic Park, King of Prussia, Pennsylvania.

Objectives: figuring out geologic time and trying to establish a sequential history for an outcrop based on field observations; reconstructing ancient faunas and environments; introducing trace fossils; using a field notebook.

Note: because the Port Kennedy Quarry (the second site here) is off limits now, this exercise is best done late in fall, during the winter, or early spring when the leaves are gone from the trees; then the two layers of rock are easily visible from the roadside.

Stop 1 – Parking lot behind Valley Forge Park visitor center. Look at the rocky cliffs on the side of the parking lot but do not attempt to climb them. You may pick up and examine pieces of rock as long as we put them back and do not remove them. At an appropriately safe portion of the outcrop, please attempt to use your Brunton compass or your smart phone app to measure dip. What is the angle of dip? What is the direction of dip? (use your compass). What would be the direction of strike on these rocks? What kind of rocks are these? (hint: we will drop some acid here). Where today would this type of rock be forming- in what depositional environment? Some of the wavy bedding in this rock may be the results of organic activity- what sorts of organisms might be involved? Take notes and draw a diagram indicating the angle and direction of dip of the rock layers in your field notebook.

Stop 2 - Port Kennedy- we will walk east down County Line Road adjacent to the parking lot (watch out for cars) approximately 100 yards, and look left into the open space where there is a rocky cliff in back (but do not enter the area and especially do not stand under the steep cliff!). This is the old Port Kennedy quarry, a very significant fossil site for 19th century paleontologists. The following specimens from this site are in the Academy of Natural Sciences collection:

Dung beetles, turtles, turkey, snipe, porcupine, beaver, pika, insectivores, coyote, red fox, gray fox, dire wolf, badger, raccoon, wolverine, puma, lynx, jaguar, cheetah?, short-faced bear, black bear, skunk, llamas, tapir, horses, peccary, deer, bison, ground sloth, mastodon, and saber-toothed cat (Gallagher, 1984, Paleocology of the Delaware Valley Region, Pt II: Cretaceous to Quaternary, The Mosasaur 2: 9-43; and Cope, ANSP Proceedings, 1895). These were found in fine-grained fill deposits within the bottom layer of the rock cliff.

Look at the rock face. What are the rocks on the bottom? What are the rocks on top? Look at the different colors of the rocks- how many layers can you see here? Which layer is older, and which layer do you think is younger? The geological history here is a little complex but very instructive; list the stages and steps that went into making the geological history of this outcrop, taking the fossils into account along with all your other observations. Draw a front view of the outcrop, showing the line (or contact) between the rock types. On another following graph page in your notebook, draw a cross-section of this outcrop, showing the relationship between the units seen head on in exposure. What does that contact represent in terms of geological time? What kind of environment do the fossils suggest?

Stop 3- Hike along Valley Creek, western edge of Valley Forge Park, Mt Misery-

As we walk along this pathway by the creek, look at some of the outcrops on the Mt. Misery side of the trail. This type of rock is called a quartzite, a metamorphic rock that was formed from sandstone by heat and pressure. Look in the rocks for vertical tubes or "pipes". These are fossils- can you hazard a guess as to how these were made? They help give us a clue about the original environment here. Draw a picture or take an image (with scale) for your field notebook. What do you think the environment here was originally?

Instructor's note - This exercise will require some questioning and discussion, and only after the basic sequence of events or the kind of environment is established should more precise details of geologic time (Cambrian, Triassic, Pleistocene) be revealed. It is listed first, because it has some of the oldest rocks considered here. This exercise was developed for Drexel University's Field Geology 301 course for upper level undergraduate majors. Evaluation was by field notebook. Reading resource: Coe, A. L. (ed), 2010, Geological Field Techniques; chapter 2, section 2.3 pgs 6-15; Chapter 9, especially sections 9.2 & 9.3.

Field Trip # 2- Rocks and Fossils of the Appalachian Valley and Ridge Province- Beltzville State Park, near Leightonton, PA.

Objectives- looking at some of the fossils and rocks of the Valley and Ridge Province and infer some of the underlying structure. We will refine our skills at formally describing rocks in the field using color charts, grain size charts, hand lenses, and other tools. We will find and collect fossils, identify them, and use them to interpret conditions of deposition. We will continue to practice compass skills. (Suggested Readings- A. L. Coe, chapters 5 - Sedimentary Rocks, and & 6, Paleontological Techniques).

Please read the hand-out on the geology (W. B. Gallagher, 1998, Geology and Paleontology on the Way to the Poconos) that you can observe in the numerous road cuts and outcrops during the drive up to the mountains on the Northeast Extension of the Pennsylvania Turnpike. Destination: Beltzville State Park, PA.

Stop 1- Beltzville Lake- Pavilion 2- Lunch stop and fossil hunting.

We will break for lunch at the shelter here and look for fossils along the beach near the lake.

Describe and illustrate some of the specimens you find here. Look at the rock type and attempt to describe it. How many different types of fossils were found here? When you are finished, we will reconvene at Pavilion 2 for fossil identification and discussion.

Stop 2- Sluiceway for Beltzville Dam

- In your field notebook under site 2- Start by describing the rocks exposed here. What general kind of rocks are these? Note color, texture, composition, fracture and any other physical features you can see in the rocks.
- Next look for fossils in the loose rock pieces and slabs along the bottom of the outcrop. What kinds of fossils are you and your classmates finding? Please list them. Draw some of the better specimens that you have found in your field notebook. How did these organisms live? How did they feed?
- Make some inference about the depositional environment here. What is your hypothesis about the reason for the fossil concentration here? Why are they concentrated in this rock? Do you think they lived here? Or did some other process concentrate the organic remains here?
- Finally, after you have discovered a good spot to find fossils, locate your spot using compass triangulation on the topographic map of the site supplied to you. Using your compass, sight on a prominent landmark (a building for example) and determine the azimuth to your site. Do this with a second landmark. Now plot the compass bearing on your map by drawing intersecting lines. The two lines will intersect at your position. You may reproduce this map as a drawing in your field notebook. Turn in the map.
- Note dip and strike of exposed rocks. Use dip and strike symbol. Note on map.

Instructor's note- contact Beltzville State Park to reserve Pavilion 2 and for maps and fossil identification handouts. You will need to contact the Beltzville Army

Corp of Engineers office for access to the sluiceway site. This involves obtaining a USACE permit, easily done on the internet.

Field Trip # 3- Paleozoic Fossils in Rounded Stones

Objectives- a basic exercise involving thinking about what fossils represent; erosion and transport of fossils, rocks, and sediments; geologic time, cycling of earth materials and the rock cycle.

This exercise was adapted for an introductory freshmen course at Rider University from a demonstration originally conceived by Warren Allmon of the Paleontological Research Institute ("Round Rocks", ucmp.berkeley.edu; this is an excellent introduction to the use of inquiry in geological education) using rounded beach pebbles from the shores of Lake Ontario as one example. But this works just as well with the Paleozoic chert pebble fossils found in New Jersey and eastern Pennsylvanian Neogene gravel deposits. It can be an introductory stand-alone exercise or used in conjunction with and after field trip #2 above to the Appalachians.

Part 1- Locate a local exposure of Neogene (Miocene, Pliocene, Pleistocene) gravels; make sure they have easily found fossils in the pebbles. Some gravel deposits are better than others; the bleached white gravels on the hilltops of the central pinelands (Apple Pie Hill for example) are not good candidates. Generally, the yellow brown gravels classified as the "Pennsauken Formation" or "Cape May Formation" (see Kuehne and Kuenhe, in press, *The Mosasaur*) will yield results. In fact, a couple of the localities described later (Big Brook, Inversand Pit) have such fossils in their deposits. Target the chert pebbles for fossils.

The sites may be a local abandoned gravel pit, a hillside exposure, the gravel in point bars and beaches along pinelands rivers (the Wading, Oswego, or Batsto Rivers). Washed gravels used in place of lawns in many South Jersey beach properties are often a rich source of such pebbles- just make sure you have the owners' permission before high-grading their gravel!

The beaches themselves are good places to explore- Sunset Beach at Cape May Point is one place to prospect. Beaches around tidal inlets are good places; there is lots of ebb and flow of currents that can move sediments, and frequently these areas are dredged for beach replenishment, bringing more coarse material to the beach surface.

Once you get your students out at the site, instruct them to collect pebbles with intriguing different textures or patterns in them. If the site is good, soon you will be presented with an assortment of Paleozoic fossils, mostly honeycomb and cup corals but also possibly bryozoan colonies, crinoid columnals, brachiopod impressions and even more rarely trilobite pieces. Or alternatively you could make a collection of these fossils yourself and present them in class.

Part 2- Have the student bring their specimens back to the classroom or lab and ask them the following questions:

1. What are the shapes in the rocks? What produces the texture or structure in the rocks?

(Here, you may wish to have some specimens available for comparison; a selection of modern corals, particularly *Fungia*, as recommended by Allmon, but I also like to include some nicer sharp-edged samples of *Favosites* or uneroded *Heliophyllum* direct from the Paleozoic outcrop for comparison. Perhaps some brachiopods or bryozoa might help also.)

2. Where was this rock first formed? (in what environment?) How did it become rock?

(this can be answered once the majority of the specimens have been identified as corals; most students are familiar with the idea of the coral reef ecosystem, and some may have visited a reef).

3. How did this rock get small? (talk about erosion, transport and deposition)

4. Why are the rocks rounded?

Instructor's note- This thought process may take a while and it behooves the instructor to be patient with students who may not have much experience with fossils or geologic concepts. However, asking and answering questions will lead the introductory students to an appreciation of uniformitarian ideas, and an introduction to the idea of erosion, transport and deposition of sediments. This could be extended to consider the larger picture of the rock cycle and geologic time.

If used as a follow up to the Appalachian trip, you might ask your students to compare their specimens from the two trips and make some conclusions about the source of the Paleozoic gravel pebbles. Alternatively, identifying the provenance of the specimens you select for comparison may help the students understand where the rocks came from. At Rider, we are fortunate in having a good teaching collection with some excellent examples from the Devonian of New York, but Devonian invertebrates from other areas (the Midwest, Canada) might work just as well for comparative identification purposes.

Resources and references-

Allmon, W. Round Rocks,
<http://ucmp.berkeley.edu>, retrieved 11/16/19.

Kuehne, W. and Kuehne, A. (in press), Paleozoic fossils of the New Jersey Coastal Plain, *The Mosasaur*, the *Journal of the Delaware Valley Paleontological Society*.

Field trip # 4- America's First Dinosaur- Haddonfield field trip exercise

Objective- placing the discovery of America's first dinosaur in a larger historical context.

Today we will visit Haddonfield, NJ in Camden County. Modern Haddonfield is a well-to-do suburb with an upscale shopping and dining district downtown. But back in 1858, Haddonfield was a quiet Quaker farming town. It was in this year that Haddonfield became famous as the site of an important fossil discovery. We will visit several sites in and around Haddonfield.

Start your notebook entry by noting date, place, name of the class (that is the name of this course), weather, general environmental conditions, etc.

Stop 1 – National Historic Landmark, Maple St. - This is near (but not exactly at) the site of the famous discovery in 1858. Read the various memorial plaques, and answer the following questions in your field notebook, making observation about the area around you.

- a. What was found here?
- b. How was it found?
- c. How big was this animal?
- d. When did it live?
- e. Name several reasons why this was a significant discovery.
- f. Who found the fossil originally, and what happened to the fossils found then?
- g. Who was involved in the 1858 excavation?
- h. Look at the skeletal diagram on one of the plaques. What bones were found? What important part was largely missing?
- i. We will descend into the stream ravine behind the memorial site- please watch your step going down. Look at the exposures of darker sediment

at the bottom along the stream. What is the name of this formation? What is its composition?

j. What is your hypothesis for the depositional environment in which this sediment was laid down? What fossils are found in the sediment? Can you draw a simple cross-section of the stratigraphy here? (there are just two layers).

k. What was the climate like back then?

Stop 2-Statue in downtown Haddonfield- This statue was sculpted by John Giannotti and went up in 2003. Please write down the answers to the following questions in your field notebook.

a. Note general anatomical features in your notebook. To what family does this creature belong?

You may draw it in your notebook if you are so inclined.

b. Size- based on what you read at the memorial site and in the assigned readings, do you think this animal as reconstructed here is full-sized?

c. Look at the pattern depicted on the skin. How do you think we might know about this soft skin pattern?

d. Stance and posture- how can we support the idea that this animal may have been able to rear back on its hind limbs?

e. How did the artist go about reconstructing this animal?

Stop 3- Municipal Building and Indian King Tavern, King's Highway- we will take a short stroll up King's Highway just a few blocks. Please try to stay together.

Site of E. D. Cope's house (now the Municipal Building)-

- a. Who was E. D. Cope?
- b. Why did he move to Haddonfield?

- c. What famous feud started as a result of O. C. Marsh's visit here in the spring of 1868?
- d. What distinction does the Indian King Tavern have in early New Jersey revolutionary war history?
- e. What religious group founded Haddonfield?

Stop 4- Challenge Grove Park- For smaller more advanced classes, an additional site might be added. At Challenge Grove Park, the nearby unnamed tributary to Cooper River exposes a fossiliferous outcrop of the Woodbury Formation. The stream gravels at this site can be productively sieved or inspected for fossils from the Late Cretaceous Woodbury Formation. Questions: what sort of fossils are found here? How did they come to be concentrated in the Woodbury Formation? What general environment do they represent?

Reference-

Gallagher, W. B. 1997, When Dinosaurs Roamed New Jersey. New Brunswick, NJ: Rutgers University Press. 176 pgs.

Field Trip # 5: Field Exercise- Big Brook, Marlboro, NJ- GEO 168, Mesozoic Ruling Reptiles

Objective- have students collect evidence and then formulate a hypothesis about paleoecology and prehistoric environmental conditions, using their evidence to support their hypothesis.

The town of Marlboro is named for exposures of marl along the banks of Big Brook. This sediment is technically known as glauconite, $K_2(Mg,Fe)_2Al_6(Si_4O_{10})_3(OH)_2$. It was widely mined in this area for fertilizer in the latter half of the 19th century, when the greensand marl mines in the marl belt of the New Jersey coastal plain produced a number of important dinosaur discoveries and other fossil specimens for the early paleontologists studying fossils in North America.

Today, Monmouth County's brooks are well known as sites for finding fossils derived from these sedimentary beds. The fossils are eroded out of the steep banks and concentrated in the stream gravels as placer deposits.

The easiest way to find these fossils is to sieve the stream gravels in a sieving box. Shovel in some stream gravel from a likely spot into your sieve box and wash the gravel in the water of the stream until all the finer material is washed away. Then inspect your sieve box for fossils. Most of what you see will be gravel (quartz pebbles, rocks, bog iron, nodules, coarse sand, etc.), but some of the remaining particles will be fossils: oyster shells, squid pens, brachiopods, and shark teeth. If we are really lucky, we might find a piece of dinosaur bone or a mosasaur tooth!

To obtain credit, write the answers to the following questions in your field report. Please word process your field report, adding any hand drawing necessary. Turn it in by end of next week.

Focus- Start by entering name, place, date, group (class name), weather. Make a map of how you came into the site and where you are. If you have questions, please ask the professor. You may work in groups of two for sieving the stream gravels.

Question #1. Sieve the stream gravel to recover the fossils contained in it. What kinds of fossils do you find here? Please list your finds in your field report. Are they trace fossils? Body fossils? Casts and/or molds? Original shell? Bone or teeth?

Question # 2. Note the cliffs along the banks. Can you see distinctive color changes? Look carefully at the sediments exposed along the stream bank. Do you see differences in texture, composition, grain size? Draw the outcrop depicting the sediment layers in your field report.

Question # 3- Why are there so many shark teeth here? Why are they fairly common?

Question 4 -plot your fossil excavation sites on the map where you have found fossils in your sieve or on top of the sediment. Try to list these by site # in your report. Are some fossils more common than others at different sites?

Question # 5. From the evidence of fossils and sediments, what is your hypothesis of the environmental conditions (including climate) at this site when the prehistoric animals lived here in the Late Cretaceous Period, 70-75 million years ago? Back it up with observations and evidence, including the kinds of fossils you found.

Checklist of fossils found here, with "Spongebob" nomenclature-

Invertebrates-

Porifera- sponge boring in oyster shells – count bored shell valve as one- Clione cretacea- "Spongebob"

Brachiopoda- lampshell- *Choristothyris plicata*

Gastropoda- usually internal molds of *Lunatia* or *Anchura*- "Gary" the snail.

Bivalvia-Oysters:

Exogyra costata- big wrinkled oyster with spiral beak and flat upper valve

Pycnodonte convexa- large inflated round smooth valve and flat upper valve

Agerostrea mesenterica- small delicate scalloped shell with wavy edges

Clams- *Cucullaea* internal molds

Pecten sp.- scallop shell

Cephalopoda- relatives of pearly nautilus and squid

Belemnites- *Belemnitella americana*- "Squidward"

Ammonites- *Baculites*; *Nostoceras*; *Placentoceras*

Crustacea- *Protocallianassa chelae* (claws)- "Mr. Crabs"

Callianassid burrows- *Ophiomorpha nodosa* trace fossils (look at sediment outcrop)

Vertebrates

Chondrichthyes- sharks, rays, and ratfish

Edaphodon- ratfish jaw plates

Ischyrohiza mira- sawfish rostral spines

Cretolamna appendiculata- ancient relative of modern lamnid sharks

Scapanorhynchus texanus- goblin shark

Squalicorax pristodontus & *S. kaupi*- extinct crow shark

Squatina- dogfish shark

Ptychotrogon

Brachyrhizodus- ray tooth

Shark and /or ray vertebrae

Osteichthyes- *Enchodus ferox*, *Anomaeodus*, *Xiphactinus*, *Paralbula*; fish vertebrae

Reptilia- mosasaur, sea turtle, softshell turtle, crocodile, plesiosaur, dinosaur pieces and teeth

Keep all your fossil specimens for your field report- you will receive an extra ten points toward your final course grade when you turn in your field report with answers to all the questions.

Instructor's note- Evaluation of this exercise is accomplished by submission of an individual field trip report, or by inclusion in a field notebook entry for more advanced classes. The field trip exercise can be extended into a classroom or lab exercise by identifying the fossils in class, counting the different taxa from specific collecting sites and quantifying the results in graphic representations using the chart functions of Excel or other quantitative applications. The objective here is to get the students to come to fundamental conclusions about concepts such as paleoenvironment, climate change, taphonomy and marine paleoecology using the evidence of their own observations and fossil sampling.

References and resources

Gallagher, W. B. 1997. *When Dinosaurs Roamed New Jersey*, Rutgers University Press, 176 pgs.

Gallagher, W. B., and Hanczaryk, P. 2019. *Paleontology of the Campanian-Maastrichtian Boundary at Marlboro, Monmouth County, New Jersey: Taphonomy, Biostratigraphy and Depositional Environments*.

Useful website: Big Brook fossils, www.njfossils.net

Field Trip #6 Exercise- Inversand Pit, Sewell, NJ

Objective- to get students to think about how sediments represent geologic time, and to teach some basic field methodology in stratigraphy.

(This version of the exercise was used for a freshman level introductory course, Introduction to Integrated Science 100. Preliminary safety instructions should be reviewed at the site).

For credit, you will need to submit your field report, following the instructions below. You may work in teams, but your field notebook entries cannot be mere copies of each other- write what you see in your own words! Be sure to write and draw legibly- others should be able to read your writing. Please print if necessary.

It will help if you take careful and complete notes- once you are back in the lab or at school, your data may not be as clear as they were in the field, unless you are taking good, accurate notes about everything you see.

1. Focus- In your notebook- Begin by entering date, name of place, group you are with, general weather conditions (briefly).

See also hand-out, "Observing and describing rocks in the field- General features"

2. Explore- Stratigraphy- The science of layered rocks.

How many distinctive layers are exposed in the pit?

How would you define a layer?

In your notebook, describe the layers of sediment in simple terms, starting at the bottom of the stack (as all good geologists do). You should note color, general composition (clay, greensand, quartz sand, etc.) and rough proportional thickness. Measure thickness if you can- estimate it for layers too steep to climb.

Now the important part- Draw a stratigraphic section, illustrating the stack of sediments from bottom to top, and identifying each layer by its physical characteristics (do this in your field notebook.). You can roughly profile the slope of the pit. Indicate on your stratigraphic cross-section where any fossils you might have found are located.

Using plastic bags provided, sample as many of the layers as possible- at least three layers must be sampled. Clearly label the plastic bags with the layer and date using the Sharpie pens provided (I will help with this if needed). We will use these samples in lab on Thursday.

Fossils found- Treat your fossils with care- they are very old and need to be handled delicately. Put them in plastic baggies or vials- labeling them helps for when you get back in the lab. For your field report you will need to make a list of the fossils you find- if you can, assign them to specific layers (the instructor will help you with this- just ask!). We will identify fossils specimens in the field and in the lab sessions.

3. Reflection- Take some time to think about what all this means.

Which layer is the oldest?

Which layer is the youngest?

In general terms, how much time do you think is represented in this stack of sediments?

(In other words, roughly how much time has passed since the bottom sediments exposed here were deposited?)

Have conditions changed in this spot, or has it always been the same here as it is today?

What is the depositional environment in the various layers? In other words what was this locality like back when some of these layers were laid down? (fossils can help with this question)

This is the last representative of a once-thriving industry- in the nineteenth century there were dozens of marl mines in southern New Jersey. What was the material used for then?

Turn in your field notebook- the report should include the sections above: stratigraphy, fossils found, reflection and applications.

Instructor's notes- More advanced versions of this exercise concentrated on producing a detailed stratigraphic section of the formations exposed in the pit excavation, including measurement of thickness by stadia rod and tape measure, and composition, grain sizes, and color of strata. Fossil concentrations should be identified on the chart and characterized by contained fossils. The formal description and drawn section is turned in as part of a field notebook, or as a separate exercise.

References: Gallagher, 1993, 1997.

Field Trip #7- Vincentown Formation Micropaleontology

Objective- introducing micropaleontology, and how microfossils are used to interpret prehistoric environmental conditions.

Part 1- Field Trip- Vincentown, Burlington County, NJ- Vincentown Formation limestone and limesand are exposed along the banks of the southeast branch of Rancocas Creek in the stratotype area. Two main exposures are located just north of Vincentown along the creek. One is accessible by footpath; the other will require permission from the Pinelands Water Company. See Gallagher (1984, 1993) for more details about the paleontology and stratigraphy.

Reaching the outcrops will take a short hike; the ascent to stream level to collect is quite steep, and students should be prepared to get wet and muddy. Be careful during the descent to stream level. The collecting is best done when the water level is low, in

the fall or summer; in spring the levels are generally too high. Students should be prepared and equipped with measuring stadia rods and tape measures, rock color and grain size charts, field notebooks, and plastic bags and small vials for collecting samples.

The fossils are abundant in the limesand outcrops, and students should take a series of samples with measurements of how far above water level the samples are located. The samples should contain enough fossiliferous material to study under the microscope back in lab. They should produce a small stratigraphic section in their notebook with formal description of the sediments sampled and position of samples indicated.

Part 2- Back in the lab, the students should take equally measured quantities of sand for study under the stereoscopic microscope. Standard texts and references should be provided to help with identification. Have students count the different fossil clasts identifiable under the microscope. This may involve changing magnifications and focus to identify various clasts of different sizes. Do this for each stratigraphic level sampled at the outcrop. The results should be presented in a table form (see example below).

Vincetown Formation- Early Paleocene, New Jersey

Taxon name	1st sample quantity	2nd sample quantity	3rd sample quantity	Description of specimens
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Examples of microfossils that should be visible in the samples will include, roughly in this order of frequency:

- Bryozoa (mostly branching colonies of *Coscinopleura digitata*, but other species as well)
- foraminifera tests (*Cibicides*, *Nodosaria*- these may require higher magnification to see)
- Small spiral worm tubes (*Spirula*).
- Echinoid (sea urchin) spine pieces and test fragments
- Small decapod (crab) claws
- Pieces of soft coral stems
- Fragments of small gastropod internal molds

On the basis of these samples, ask the students to think about the environment represented by the fossils. One way to approach this is to ask students about the type of sediment this is; carbonate rocks of this type tends to occur in warmer marine environments. Today such environments would be found farther south; a sample of New Jersey beach sand can help make this point. Today no carbonate sands are being deposited along the New Jersey coast, so obviously conditions have changed in Southern New Jersey.

The endpoint of this discussion should consider the nature of climate and environmental change. Finding this marine deposit 50 miles inland from the present-day shoreline suggests that sea level was higher in the early Paleocene Epoch than it is today; what factors could have caused this?

A deeper question concerns the succession of fossil faunas in the Paleocene coastal plain deposits. As seen in the subjacent Hornerstown Formation below the Vincentown Formation, several fossils assemblages show a decreasing diversity of fossil faunas, and a change from Mesozoic fossil forms to different Paleocene organisms. The Vincentown Limesand fossil fauna shows a remarkable diversity of organisms, particularly among the bryozoa (Gallagher, 1993). In conjunction with results of the student studies in Exercise 7 above, the lab discussion could then turn to considerations of mass extinction and recovery of the biota from mass extinction.

Field trip 8: Barrier beach island environments and beach profile at Corson's Inlet, NJ

Objective- Barrier beach islands are dynamic geologic environments. This week at the beach, you will collect several sets of data related to physical oceanographic processes, depositional environments and the distribution of organisms in those environments. Today, you will analyze the different data sets and associated physical processes and investigate how they influence the shoreline and how the organisms

living here might become part of the fossil record. You will be working in groups as last week. However, you should still turn in your own field notebook report.

Start your notebook entry with the location, date, name of the group, weather, general conditions (high tide/low tide? rough surf? etc.).

Part A

What do you notice about the width of the beach immediately south vs. immediately north of the jetty? What might cause this pattern of sand distribution?

Let's do a simple measurement on a drifting object and observe its movement. Toss a large navel orange into the waves as far as it can be thrown. Measure how long it takes to drift north or south over a premeasured distance (say, 100 meters) using cell phones or stop watches. What process is causing the orange to move along the coast?

We have seen that in the geologic record as in the section we studied at Inversand Pit, sedimentation is heavily influenced by relative sea level. Transgressions are times when sea level is rising; regressions are times when sea level lowers.

What phase of sea level change are we now in?

Barrier Beach section

1. In Exercise 7, you measured elevation changes along a vertical stratigraphic section including several formations laid down in different depositional environments. This week we will measure elevation changes along a transect on the beach with the equipment provided. From your data, you now want to draw a beach profile (cross-section) along your transect line, on the graph paper side of your notebook. Discuss in your group how you would draw the profile, given the data you collect, i.e., what do you have to do with your data in order to generate a beach profile? Explain the procedure in your notes. How might this profile change in the short term due to changes in wave energy or wind?

2. We will look at the environments in a typical barrier beach island in a transect across the dunes and around the inlet. Note the typical sediment, flora and fauna associated with each environment; how would these environments and their contained sediments and organisms look in the geologic record?

Consider Walther's law- "The principle that when depositional environments migrate laterally, sediments of one environment come to lie on top of sediments of an adjacent environment." (from Stanley and Luczaj, 2015).

What does this mean for the sedimentary record of the Barrier Island system and all of its components? How would this express itself in the geologic record underneath us? Can you draw the relationships that might result in the form of a cross-section?

Part B- You will want to make observations dealing with 1) depositional environments (sand, mud, etc.) and 2) taphonomy- are the organisms we find likely to become part of the fossil record?

1. Depositional environments- we will look at the ocean, beach, the inlet, the lagoon and lagoon beach, salt marsh, etc. Refer to your hand-out, especially the block diagram, to understand the relationship between these environments. We will want to make separate notes on each, generally describing sediments, etc. What physical factors are dominant in each environment? Consider closely sediment type, sorting, composition, etc. Draw a map of the area if this helps.

2. Organisms and taphonomy- what organisms can we find in each environment?

How likely is it a species will be preserved as a fossil? (i.e., does it have hard parts?)

Organisms with segmented skeletons are intermediate in preservational potential.

You can make an overall list with three categories:

Likely to be preserved	Intermediate
Low chance of being preserved (high chance of preservation) (50-50 %)	(probably not)

Consider these as sedimentary particles- which organisms have the best chance of contributing to the geologic record? How might they be preserved? What percentage will become fossils?

Barrier island and shore face profile and terminology adapted from USACE.

Part C -Finally let's get together as a group back by the jetty and think about what we have seen today. What happened along this coast in October 2012? What implication does this have for development along the barrier beach islands.? This area supports a \$40 billion/year tourist industry. Does this justify expensive federal programs such as beach replenishment? Or taxpayer assistance to rebuild beach homes? What is the impact of human activities on the natural environment here? Does dredging affect the local benthic organisms?

Instructor's notes- This exercise was initially developed for Rider's Marine Life Through Time MAR 210, a class for intermediate level undergraduate majors, and modified for a more general application for Drexel Geology 301, Field Geology, an upper level majors course. Although this version is for Corson's Inlet State Park in Cape May County, the same basic exercise was also conducted at Manasquan Beach, Manasquan Inlet and Fisherman's Cove along Manasquan Bay. An earlier version of this exercise designed for high school students was conducted at Island Beach State Park in Ocean County for University of Pennsylvania's summer Discovery Program.

The intent here is to demonstrate to students a variety of coastal environments, consider how barrier islands are dynamic changing sedimentary systems, how organisms are adapted to specific habitats, and the chances of various organisms becoming part of the fossil record. This is an introduction to the subdiscipline of taphonomy, the “laws of burial”, or how living organisms become fossils. A lot of this has to do with information loss and preservation, usually preservation of organisms with hard parts. Calculating the percentage of organisms likely to become fossils because of possession of hard parts (mollusks) versus those soft bodied forms (worms, jellyfish, algae) or segmented organisms (arthropods, vertebrates) that are less likely to be preserved brings home to students the biases in the fossils record. Considering how remains might be moved, disarticulated or otherwise modified can add to a better appreciation of what a fossil deposit actually represents.

For more advanced classes, instructors might be inclined to introduce students to the “Aktuo-Paleontologie” school of taphonomy, as developed by the Senckenberg Research Institute associated with the Senckenberg Museum of Natural History in Frankfurt, Germany (Schafer, 1972). This line of research involves direct observation of modern organisms interacting with each other and with their sedimentary environments, and how they might become preserved in the geologic record. This is by extension an example of uniformitarianism, the basic geologic assumption that the present is the key to the past.

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